

DIGITAL FINANCIAL TECHNOLOGIES

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Digital technologies have become so embedded in our lives that today not only our daily activities, but also the development of socio-economic spheres cannot be imagined without them. Naturally, as in other areas, the introduction of digital technologies in the financial sector is fundamentally changing its operations. Digital technology is a modern way of doing business. In it, a large set of data in digital form and the process of their processing serve as the main factor of production and management. Using the obtained results in practice makes it possible to achieve much greater efficiency compared to traditional forms of management.

For example, various automatic production processes, 3D technology, cloud technologies. It is possible to mention the provision of remote medical services, the production and delivery of products with the help of smart technologies, the processes of storing and selling various goods. What does the transition to digital technologies mean? - question can be answered as follows:

- By the transition to digital technologies, we understand the establishment of a completely new type of development of society and economy based on computers and knowledge:
- Mobile social networks, cloud technologies that implement work with governments as the main components of the process of transition to digital technologies. sensor networks, the Internet of Things and artificial intelligence technologies can be cited as examples:

- The above-mentioned technologies together allow to create "smart" objects and processes (smart state, smart house, smart city, healthcare, transport and entrepreneurship).

Digital technologies are manifested in the following systemic changes.

Implementation of virtualization processes in education, production and management:

- the emergence of the Internet of Things and distance education;
- blockchain technologies and various processes carried out by means of it;
- the process of development and the creation of an opportunity to run an independent business;
- the emergence of a new banking-money-credit system and banking activities;
- implementation of the ICO (Initial Coin Offering) process, which allows attracting large investments;
- emergence of new personnel and new jobs;
- emergence of a new corporate culture;
- implementation of new management and control methods;
- finding content in large databases (big data);
- implementation of artificial intelligence and intellectual management systems;
- emergence of cryptocurrencies as an independent monetary unit;
- occurrence of other great opportunities;

The application of digital technologies in the financial sector has led to the further development of tax, banking, insurance and other financial sectors. For the introduction and systematic implementation of technologies in these areas, the head of state adopted Decision No. PQ-4699 dated April 28, 2020 "On measures for the wide implementation of digital economy and electronic government". The application of technologies in the field of finance is mainly called FinTech (Financial Technology).

Financial technology (Fintech) is a term used to describe new technology designed to improve and automate the delivery and use of financial services. At its core, fintech helps companies, business owners and consumers better manage their financial activities, processes and lives. This can be done with the help of special programs and algorithms that are increasingly being installed on smartphones. The word fintech is a combination of "financial technology". Currently, many foreign countries have extensive experience in introducing "fintech".

As of November 2021, there were 10,755 fintech (financial technology) startups in the US, making it the region with the largest number of fintech startups globally. For comparison, there were 9,323 such startup projects in Europe, the Middle East and Africa, and 6,268 in the Asia Pacific region.

By introducing "FinTech" to the financial sector, the following advantages can be achieved:

Financing will be more convenient;

Efficiency increases;

Payments are made faster;

State and citizens' funds are saved;

Risk management is better;

Financial transactions will be simplified;

In our opinion, together with this, the rapid development of digital technologies and the increase in the need for qualified specialists in the field require the establishment of a separate study area on FinTech (Financial Technologies) in higher education institutions. First of all, this opens a wider way for the system to be provided with potential personnel. World experience shows that financial technologies help to accelerate the financial sector, at the same time, increase the efficiency of the "e-government" and the development of the "digital economy" in the country, and most importantly, reduce the share of the hidden economy.

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